

Measuring the Impact of Social Work on Saudi Society

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Abstract:

Background: The level of impact that the field of social work has in Saudi is particularly not well captured in existing literature.

Aim: Therefore, this research aims to measure the impact of the profession on the Saudi society.

Methodology: The research surveyed 780 inhabitants of the cities of Riyadh, Medina, and Hail using a validated questionnaire then measured the responses on a three-point Likert scale.

Results: Its findings revealed that social work is not well conceptualized by the people of Saudi, that the impact of the profession varied across multiple sectors, and that negative cultural perspectives towards the field prevail, indicating that the profession was not impactful in the kingdom.

Keywords: Saudi Arabia, Impact, Society, Social Work, Perceptions.

MEASURING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL WORK ON SAUDI SOCIETY

Social work is a valuable component in protecting vulnerable populations and enhancing overall human wellbeing. Anchored on the tenets of human rights and social justice, the profession seeks to empower persons, their families, and entire communities to triumph over challenges, be they physical, psychological, social, or economic (Onoh & Ogbuagu, 2023). The field plays a major role in protecting the vulnerable and supplementing wellbeing but its impact on societies is often not well studied. The shortfall in the literature on the impact of the profession on societies is more profound in Saudi society.

In Saudi, the profession traces its origins to the mid-20th century. At first, the profession was introduced in schools to build and develop the social performance of children, prevent them from falling into problems that could lead to deviance, and overcome any family or societal issues they may harbor (Alotaibi et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the field evolved over time and developed beyond its use solely in education as the Kingdom underwent rapid social and economic transformation. Gradually it took on the role of supporting individuals in adjusting to planned social developments and shifting social frameworks, subsequently promoting a sense of community and social development (Mahmoud, 2022). Saudi Arabia continues to implement a range of social and economic reforms as outlined in its national plan, Vision 2030. Therefore, measuring the impact of this profession becomes even more crucial as it would help understand the extent to which the field continues to contribute to national development, the citizen's wellbeing, and social cohesion.

This research will measure the impact that the profession of social work has on the Saudi society. It will apply three primary dimensions that are interrelated. The first dimension will be the concept of the social work profession and the professionals in it. The second dimension will be that of the areas that the field is most effective in. The third dimension will be on the societal and cultural attitudes held by the Saudi society towards the profession. Together, these dimensions will contribute to quantifying how impactful the profession has been on the Saudi society. The dimensions will present how the field is thought of, and the areas in which the profession is considered to have the most impact. Also, they will measure underlying factors determining how much of an influence the profession has on the Saudi society.

The research will gather views from the general public to measure the impact of the profession. Its findings will be valuable to practitioners, educators, and policymakers alike. Stakeholders in the field can use the study's findings to identify areas of strength and weakness in practice, which will support identification of avenues to make the profession more impactful. While the findings will be useful to stakeholders, they will be even more beneficial the general public since making the profession more impactful will allow it to better advance its aims, which center around the promotion of social justice, protection of the vulnerable, and the advancement of overall well-being of society.

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL WORK AND SOCIAL WORKERS ON SOCIETY

The social work profession and those who work in it can have a substantial impact on society. The profession can impact society by advancing social justice and facilitating protections for marginalized groups (Farooq, 2025). It is a profession that dedicates itself to helping persons and groups to overcome the challenges they face to experience enhanced wellbeing (Farooq, 2025). Anchored on the key tenets of respecting differences and promoting human rights, the profession commits to promoting changes directed towards availing equal access to opportunities and resources that people need to live dignified lives in society.

Practitioners in the field undertake a variety of initiatives to support the marginalized populations and facilitate social justice. For instance, they provide direct support to individuals in need of assistance and engage in advocacy to call for changes in policies that contribute to systemic issues (Farooq, 2025). They also deal with social issues such as poor mental wellbeing, disability, drug abuse, and domestic violence (Smith, 2018). These professionals also engage in caring for the ageing, child welfare, and supporting justice and correctional functions (Kesri, 2021). While undertaking these initiatives social workers are deemed to be operating at either, the micro, mezzo, or macro level (Mattocks, 2018). Each of these three levels see the initiatives undertaken by social workers have varied impacts either on individuals or entire societies.

At the micro level, the impact of the profession and professionals is more direct, felt by individuals in communities. The micro level sees social work personnel provide services such as case management, counseling, and crisis interventions to either individuals or families (Mattocks, 2018). At the Mezzo level, however, their impact broadens as they work with communities, organizations, teams, along with any other formalized groups such as schools and correctional institutions (Forenza & Eckert, 2018). Impact at the macro level is the broadest, with social work personnel now pushing initiatives at the city, national, or even global level (Forenza & Eckert, 2018). It is at this level that the profession and the professionals within it start influencing broader systems, seeking to resolve systemic issues such as biases. Operating at the three levels facilitates the capacity of the profession to have influence that spans across entire communities.

Overall, various dimensions demonstrate the impact of this field and professionals within it. Impact can be seen in the enhanced social wellbeing they facilitate, when professionals in the field promote resilience and social inclusion in communities (Kesri, 2021). Additionally, it also appears through the promotion of economic stability, when they facilitate stability of families and education to support economic advancement (Smith, 2018). Moreover, the impact of the profession can also be observed through the lens of community development, when they strengthen community capacities (Smith, 2018). It can also be observed through the lens of policy influence when social workers engage in the shaping of welfare policies and advocacy against discriminatory policies that marginalize

vulnerable populations (Kesri, 2021). The impact of the field translates to building a just and equitable society for everyone in it.

SOCIAL WORK IN SAUDI ARABIA

The origins of this discipline in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia remain a thing of debate. There are scholars that argue that the field began in 1962 as way to support the vulnerable in society (Althumali, 2021). However, others have presented contradictory claims that it was launched much earlier, in 1955, after two professionals were employed by the Kingdom to oversee schools and their activities relevant to social work. Other researchers also present claims that the profession started a year earlier in Saudi, marked by the opening of a juvenile care center in 1954, after which it was extended into schools (Alsehaimi, 2025). Even with these differences, however, the general consensus is that, in Saudi, the profession initially started in the field of education (Alotaibi et al., 2020; Althumali, 2021; Mahmoud, 2022). Currently, the profession has expanded into multiple other fields in the kingdom.

Social work has expanded into medicine, child welfare, and criminal justice in Saudi Arabia. In the field of medicine, the profession has been integral in facilitating integrated care, which is defined by access to comprehensive care over the continuum of care (Alsehaimi, 2025). In child welfare, social work has been instrumental in launching and facilitating child care policies and programs. With respect to the field of criminal justice, the profession has particularly been integral in advancing gender justice by advocating for greater rights and protections for women against gender-based violence (Noor, 2024). Within the field of criminal justice as well, the profession is also involved with the rehabilitation of juvenile offenders (Alsehaimi, 2025). The field supports multiple sectors in Saudi Arabia, facilitating the seamless operations of systems.

Nevertheless, the profession still largely remains underdeveloped in the kingdom. The field is yet to permeate all sectors in which it would be relevant and impactful, such as environmental conservation, where it has minimal impact (Alsehaimi, 2023). Moreover, there still remains some shortcomings in social work education provision since it does not adequately prepare students for practice (Althumali, 2021; Mahmoud, 2022). Therefore, while social work has advanced, there still remains a massive gap between its current state and potential.

STUDY QUESTIONS

Social work has existed in Saudi Arabia for decades, permeating multiple fields in the kingdom. The current study will focus on the impact this profession has in Saudi Arabia. It attempts to answer the overarching question, “What is the impact of social work on the Saudi society?” It breaks down this question into three secondary questions;

- How clear is the concept of social work and the social worker in Saudi society?
- What are the areas in which social workers are most effective in Saudi Arabia?
- What are the social and cultural attitudes towards the social work profession in Saudi Arabia?

STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary aim of the current study is to measure the impact of social work in the Saudi Arabian society. Nonetheless, to more articulately understand this impact, this study will focus on three key secondary objectives. These secondary objectives are:

- To measure the clarity of the concepts of social work and the social worker in the Saudi society.
- To measure the most effective areas of social work as perceived by Saudi society.
- To measure societal and cultural attitudes towards the social work profession.

The three secondary objectives facilitate the establishment of the impact that social work has on Saudi society.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will present findings that will prove significant to policymaking, practice, and education. Under policymaking, the current study will provide an evidence basis for making social work more impactful by introducing legislation that integrates social work more deeply into national development initiatives. On the other hand, within the realm of practice, the findings will enhance the awareness of professionals in the field on how their profession is viewed in the society they inhabit, whether the population views their contribution as substantial. Lastly, under education, the findings could inform initiatives geared towards redesigning the social work training curriculum to make the profession more impactful in society. Besides the practical significance, however, the study also makes important theoretical contributions. It adds on to the existing body of literature on the profession in Saudi Arabia, and the Arab world as a whole, which is relatively limited. The research examines the views on the conceptualization of the profession, its functional areas, and societal perceptions in the kingdom. This analysis enables the research to contribute to a localized theoretical comprehension of the impact of the profession that is specific to Saudi culture and Islamic values, a component largely missing in existing social work literature.

STUDY CONCEPTS

Social Work and the Social Worker

As concepts, the social work profession and professionals in it have changed over time. Previous definitions were often criticized for perceived western bias, emphasis on individualism, lack of strong theoretical underpinnings, and failure to recognize local knowledge (Ornellas et al., 2018). Subsequently, this led to a review by the International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW) and the International Schools of Social Work (IASSW). The new definition defines the profession as "...a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people" (Ornellas et al., 2018, p.3). It views respect for diversity, collective responsibility, human rights, and social justice as integral for the discipline. Forenza and Eckert (2018) detail that the professionals in the field help people, families, and communities towards restoring their capacity to optimally function socially, establishing conditions that are supportive of communities that are in need.

Areas of Social Work Practice

The field of social work is broad, with multiple other fields of practice. These fields of practice can be categorized into four general groups. The first is that of child welfare, which also supports initiatives targeting the family (Schulze-Krüdener, 2019). The second is the much broader group, for adults in general, which incorporates the provision of support for rehabilitation, drug related issues, and unemployment, among other issues. There also is field of geriatric care under the profession, which directs its services to the elderly, serving elderly care homes and hospices (Schulze-Krüdener, 2019). Lastly there is the component of social work that operates in the healthcare system, offering assistance with mental and physical disabilities. In all contexts, social work retains the dual focus of assisting individuals and identifying the systemic issues promoting inequality and injustice (Papadopoulos, 2022). The dual focus is guided by the ideas of privilege, oppression, power, and diversity.

Social Perceptions of Social Work

Social perceptions of this profession refer to the views that the public generally holds regarding the field. They include views on the education and training levels required for professionals in the field, the need for licensing, and whether the field accommodates individuals from both sexes (Osmanaga, 2019; Rowe et al., 2023). They also include public sentiment on the functions that professionals in the field are expected to take on, and the acceptability of seeking help (Rowe et al., 2023). The perceptions on the profession held by individuals in society are important to capture since the field is heavily involved with the general public (Osmanaga, 2019). If social perceptions are positive, there will emerge a strong relationship between the professionals in the field and the public, subsequently enhancing the service levels to yield better outcomes. On the

contrary, if perceptions are poor, public relations would be strained to result minimize impact.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used an electronic questionnaire to gather data to measure the impact of the profession on the Saudi Arabian society. The electronic questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative data and was sent to the study participants via email. The questionnaire focused on three key dimensions to establish the impact of the profession in the kingdom. The first included, the public's understanding of the concept of the field and practitioners in it. The second dimension related to their view on where the field was most effective, while the final dimension was concerned with the social and cultural perceptions the public hold towards the profession. The random sample of the Saudi society chosen to participate in the survey hailed from the three major cities of Riyadh, Medina, and Hail. The sample constituted social influencers. This group was specifically selected since the researcher considered them to be more conversant with the questions posed and the nature of the discipline in Saudi Arabia.

Target Population

The targeted population in the current study was males and females residing in three cities in the kingdom, spread across the western, central, and northern regions, Medina, Riyadh, and Hail, respectively. The study sought to assess the impact of the profession in Saudi society, and the target population would facilitate gathering data that is more representative. A convenience sample of 780 individuals was randomly selected from the target population, with selection based on the kind of questions contained in the study. Participation in the study was limited only to members of the target population holding, at least, a university degree.

Data Collection

Collection of data used a questionnaire. An electronic questionnaire sent to participants via email was the primary data collection instrument and the questionnaire was designed to align with the objectives of the study. Validation of the questionnaire was undertaken using feedback from the researcher's university professors and knowledgeable experts in the field of social work. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was then calculated to gauge the internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire, yielding a value of 0.91, which was an acceptable level of reliability. Some additional revisions were made to the questionnaire to improve the language, style, content, and format. The questionnaire was then administered to the 780 participants, and participants were asked to indicate how much they agreed with the questionnaire items which were structured using a three-point Likert scale.

Data analysis

Data analysis for the current study was undertaken using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. It included an analysis of the demographic data and the computation of mean scores for the response values of the participants. When coding the response options, “scarcely = disagree = low” and was assigned a value of 1, “sometimes = to some extent = medium” was assigned a value of 2, while “always = agree = high” was assigned the value 3. The proportions of the responses for each item were also computed and presented as percentage to denote proportions more clearly.

Piloting the Questionnaires

For piloting, the study questionnaire was initially administered to a random sample of 40 participants. Unlike the main study, which used an electronic questionnaire, the pilot study involved the use of in-person sessions with paper-based questionnaires. The researcher collaborated with a team of research assistants to explain the purpose and nature of the questionnaire to participants during a two-hour session. Questionnaires were then distributed to the participants, completed under supervision, and immediately collected. Adjustments were made to the number and type of questions, as well as the data collection procedures based on the feedback received. These adjustments helped improve the clarity, accuracy, and efficiency of the main data collection process.

RESULTS

The Concept of the Social Work Profession and the Social Worker

Table 1 presents the results on the respondents’ conceptualization of the social work profession and professionals. 53.1% of the participants interviewed reported that the work of the social worker can scarcely be done by anyone without specialization while 22.3% reported that it can always be done without specialization. On the other hand, 46.9% held the view that the social work profession scarcely contributed to the development of society while less than half of that, 21.9% held the sentiment that the profession always contributed positively to the development of the Saudi society. 47.7% of the respondents held the view that social work sometimes required study and specialization while only 18.1% responded that social work always required studying and specializing. 40.4% of the respondents also felt that professionals in the field only sometimes required special skills and knowledge. Comparatively, 25% of the respondents were of the view that social workers always have special knowledge and skills.

18% of the respondents reported that the role of professionals in the field was always clear and understood by society, while 43.8% held the view that the role of the professionals scarcely was clear. On the other hand, 45.0% of the respondents reported that social workers scarcely help people solve their problems, with far fewer respondents, 14.6% affirming that they always helped people solve their problems. Comparing social work to volunteer work, 20.8% of the respondents reported that the work of a social worker is different from that

of a volunteer work. However, the respondents did relate social work to volunteer work to some extent with 44.2% holding the view that the two were no different. Lastly, 49.2% of the respondents reported that social work was scarcely an important profession in society. A far lesser proportion, 18.5%, saw social work as an ever-important profession in society.

N	Items	Response	Frequency	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Anyone can do the work of a social worker without a specialization.	Always	174	22.3	1.72	1.292	8
		Sometimes	192	24.6			
		Scarcely	414	53.1			
2	The social work profession contributes to the development of society.	Always	171	21.9	2.25	1.128	5
		Sometimes	243	31.2			
		Scarcely	366	46.9			
3	Social work is a profession that requires study and specialization.	Always	141	18.1	2.30	1.081	3
		Sometimes	372	47.7			
		Scarcely	267	34.2			
4	Social workers have special knowledge and skills.	Always	195	25.0	1.90	1.022	7
		Sometimes	270	34.6			
		Scarcely	315	40.4			
5	The role of the social worker is clear and understood by society.	Always	141	18.1	2.26	1.029	4
		Sometimes	297	38.1			
		Scarcely	342	43.8			
6	A social worker helps people solve their problems.	Always	114	14.6	2.30	0.993	2
		Sometimes	315	40.4			
		Scarcely	351	45.0			
7	The work of a social worker is no different from volunteer work.	Always	162	20.8	2.23	1.075	6
		Sometimes	273	35.0			
		Scarcely	345	44.2			
8	Social work is an important profession in society.	Always	144	18.5	2.31	1.108	1
		Sometimes	252	32.3			
		Scarcely	384	49.2			
The overall mean of the concept of the social work profession and the social worker participation among the study participants.					2.16	1.09	

Table 1: The Concept of the Social Work Profession and the Social Worker

The Most Effective Areas of Social Work Practice

Table 2 presents the views of the participants on the effectiveness of the profession in different fields of practice. 52.7% of the participants agreed that the profession was effective in family protection centers, while only 14.2% disagreed that social work was effective in these centers. There was a strong recognition of the contribution of the profession to safeguarding families and resolving domestic issues, particularly with the item having the highest proportion of respondents agreeing. Within the context of orphanages and childcare centers, however, 47.7% disagreed that social work was effective while only 16.2% felt it was effective. With this being the item with the highest proportion of respondents disagreeing, it was clear that many participants saw that social work had limited impact or visibility in the child welfare sector. Nonetheless, under charitable organizations, only 12.7% disagreed that social work was effective while a much more substantial 41.9% agreed that social work was effective in charitable organizations.

On the other hand, only 26.5% of the respondents agreed that social work professionals were effective in hospitals and health centers while 38.1% disagreed. Within the context of elderly care homes and rehabilitation centers for people with disability, agreement that social work was effective in this area notably high at 45.4% while only 16.2% disagreed that social work was effective. 47.3% disagreed that social work was effective in schools and universities, with only 13.1% of the respondents agreeing that it was. A larger proportion, 23.1% agreed that social work was effective in prisons and correctional facilities whereas nearly half, 48.1% disagreed. Nonetheless, despite agreeing that social work was effective in some areas, respondents also reported high levels of general uncertainty with the efficacy of social work. A substantial 41.5% indicated that they did not specifically know which area social work was most effective in.

N	Items	Response	Frequency	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Family protection centers	Agree	411	52.7	2.38	1.092	1
		To some extent	258	33.1			
		Disagree	111	14.2			
2	Orphanages and childcare centers	Agree	126	16.2	2.32	1.053	2
		To some extent	282	36.2			
		Disagree	372	47.7			
3	Charitable organizations	Agree	327	41.9	2.29	0.923	3
		To some extent	354	45.4			
		Disagree	99	12.7			
4	Hospitals and Health Centers	Agree	207	26.5	1.97	1.214	8
		To some extent	276	35.4			
		Disagree	297	38.1			
5	Elderly care homes and Rehabilitation centers for people with disabilities	Agree	354	45.4	2.29	1.022	4
		To some extent	300	38.5			
		Disagree	126	16.2			
6	Schools and Universities	Agree	102	13.1	2.27	0.898	5
		To some extent	309	39.6			
		Disagree	369	47.3			
7	Prisons and correctional facilities	Agree	180	23.1	2.25	1.161	6
		To some extent	225	28.8			
		Disagree	375	48.1			
8	I don't know	Agree	324	41.5	2.15	1.130	7
		To some extent	246	31.5			
		Disagree	210	26.9			
The overall mean of the most effective areas of social work.					2.24	1.061	

Table 2: The Most Effective Areas of Social Work Practice

Societal and Cultural Attitudes Towards the Social Work Profession

Table 3 presents the results on the perspectives that the Saudi society hold towards the profession. 48.8% of the participants indicated that it was not socially acceptable for a person to seek help from a social worker while only 20.0% highlighted that it was socially acceptable to seek help. Interestingly, 51.5% of the respondents reported that people had a low sense of fear of the stigma of dealing with social workers while 12.3% of the respondents highlighted that there was a

high level of fear of stigma. However, with respect to the compatibility of social work with the Islamic culture and values, 48.1% of the respondents reported that there was low compatibility while only 19.6% reported that there was high compatibility between social work and the Islamic culture and values. On the other hand, with regards to whether the social worker respect community values and traditions, 46.2% of the respondents pointed out social workers displayed a low level of respect. Only 18.8% responded that the professionals in social work displayed a high level of respect to the values and traditions of the Saudi Arabian communities.

48.1% of the participants endorsed the notion that the profession is a suitable profession for both men and women, while only 16.2% thought the profession was unsuitable for both sexes. Additionally, 47.3% of the participants held the view that seeking help from a social worker can cause social embarrassment, with only 13.1% holding a contrarian perspective. 48.5% of the respondents deemed that the family was best placed to solve social problems without the intervention of social work, while only 11.5% of the respondents held a contrasting view. Lastly, 45.4% of the respondents highlighted that there was a low likelihood they would encourage others to study social work, with only 19.2% reporting a high likelihood they would.

N	Items	Response	Frequency	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	It is socially acceptable for a person to seek help from a social worker.	High	156	20.0	2.29	1.126	5
		Medium	243	31.2			
		Low	381	48.8			
2	People fear the stigma of dealing with a social worker.	High	96	12.3	2.39	1.047	1
		Medium	282	36.2			
		Low	402	51.5			
3	The social work profession is compatible with our Islamic culture and values.	High	153	19.6	2.28	1.110	6
		Medium	252	32.3			
		Low	375	48.1			
4	The social worker respects community values and traditions.	High	147	18.8	2.27	1.072	7
		Medium	273	35.0			
		Low	360	46.2			
5	Social work is a suitable profession for both men and women.	High	375	48.1	2.32	1.058	4
		Medium	279	35.8			
		Low	126	16.2			
6	Seeking help from a social worker can cause social embarrassment.	High	369	47.3	2.34	1.002	3
		Medium	309	39.6			
		Low	102	13.1			
7	The family is best placed to solve social problems without the intervention of social work.	High	378	48.5	2.37	0.994	2
		Medium	312	40.0			
		Low	90	11.5			
8	Encourage others to study social work.	High	150	19.2	2.26	1.067	8
		Medium	276	35.4			
		Low	354	45.4			
The overall mean of the societal and cultural attitudes towards the social work profession.					2.30	1.076	

Table 3: Societal and Cultural Attitudes Towards the Social Work Profession

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

With regards to the conceptualization of social work and social work professionals, a majority of the respondents viewed social work as an important profession in society. This view aligns with that from Hanley (2025), which presented findings that the English public view the work done by social workers as worthwhile, comparable to nurses, teachers, and the police. It also aligns with public perceptions in the Kazakh society, where the public mostly viewed that the profession is necessary in society (Tulebayev, 2021). Majority of the respondents also held the view that not everyone can do the work of a social worker without a specialization. Literature from Albania and England also highlights similar perceptions held by the public in these regions, wherein social work is deemed to require some sort of education, licensing, and specialization (Hanley, 2025; Osmanaga, 2019). The respondents in the current study recognized the value in the profession and acknowledged that it did require a specific skillset to effectively perform, similar to how the general public views social work in other nations.

Nonetheless, while the respondents viewed the field as valuable and necessary in society, they also predominantly held the view that the profession only scarcely makes contributions to the development of society. This view differed from the perspectives held by the English society in Hanley (2025), but aligned with the perspectives generally held in Nigerian society, as presented by Gray and Amadasun (2024). The field is not uniformly perceived as contributing to developing societies in other nations outside Saudi Arabia. Nonetheless, it does appear that there is some public consensus that social work rarely helps people solve their problems. Even while acknowledging the potential for social work to help solve people's problems in society, research on the English, Kazakh, Nigerian, and American directly asserted or implied that social work is effective in helping people solve their problems (Amadasun, 2021; LeCroy & Kaplan, 2022; Tulebayev, 2021). These insights aligned with the findings of the current study in which majority also held the opinion that that social workers rarely help people solve their problems.

Regarding the most effective areas of the profession, responses in the current study indicated that the field was highly effective in family protection centers, elderly care homes, and rehabilitation centers for people with disabilities. On the other hand, social work was not seen to be effective in the areas of childcare, hospitals and health centers, schools and universities, and prisons and correctional facilities. The recognition of social work's impact in only a few fields by society is, nonetheless, a common occurrence, reported in studies on the English and Turks (Rowe et al., 2023; Bolgün & Şahin, 2019). Social work's impact is recognized mainly in areas related to child welfare or elder care in these societies, whereas in Saudi Arabia, the contributions of social work are not recognized in areas of childcare. This difference could possibly be explained by cultural factors but attempting to identify why such a difference exists would be

beyond the scope of the current study. Regardless of the difference it is evident that the recognition of the practical impact of social work is not even across multiple sectors, possibly since its role in all sectors remain underdeveloped.

Under the sociocultural attitudes towards the field, the majority of the participants held the view that it was not socially acceptable for a person to seek help from a professional. They further went on to view seeking help from a professional as a cause for social embarrassment. Therefore, the culture within Saudi society substantially influenced perceptions on help-seeking and its acceptability in the general public. Existing research backs the influence of cultural perceptions on help-seeking attitudes in different societies. For instance, Al-Ma'seb et al. (2020) highlighted a similar issue in the Arab nation of Kuwait, where there was also public stigma associated with seeking help from social workers. Nonetheless, the issue of negative social attitudes limiting help seeking is not only confined to the Arab world. Studies also highlight social stigma as a barrier to help seeking in different other communities, such as the Anishnaabe, an indigenous group in Canada, and African Americans (Estifanos & Farmer, 2018; Pourcelot et al., 2025). Negative sociocultural attitudes towards help seeking are not unique to the Saudi society, but they influence the likelihood of individuals seeking assistance from social workers.

Majority of the participants in this study responded that the profession of social work was incompatible with Islamic culture and values and that social workers did not respect community values. Nonetheless, existing studies on the compatibility of social work with Islamic culture indicate the contrary. Albrithen (2023), for instance, notes that the principles of the field are global and do not conflict in any way with the Islamic or Arabic cultures. Schmid and Sheikhzadegan (2022) also highlight how the field of social work has been characterized by growing sensitivity to issues of religiosity and spirituality as the years progress. While existing studies do highlight that the field is compatible with Islamic culture and values and respectful of Arabic community values, it would not be suitable to be entirely dismissive of the sentiments obtained from respondents in the study. There is always a possibility that the current version of the profession practiced in Saudi Arabian society is yet to be fully adapted to cultural contexts, hence the sentiments.

Finally, study respondents predominantly expressed the sentiment that the family is best placed to solve social problems. This aligned with the overarching societal attitudes towards help seeking, which generally stigmatize seeking help from social workers. The combination of the negative sociocultural attitudes towards help seeking, the view that social work is incompatible with religion, and the preference for turning to the family for help rather than social workers likely explain the subdued impact of social work in the Saudi society identified in the current study. While the field is respected in principle, the Saudi society is yet to accept the practice into its culture, which emphasizes family autonomy and reservations in help seeking.

CONCLUSION

This study measured social work's impact on the Saudi society. It examined three dimensions, the concept of profession and the professionals in it, areas that social work practice is most effective in, and societal perceptions of the profession. The findings reveal that the field does not have a significant impact on Saudi society, even though it has achieved substantial recognition in society. Respondents recognize that the field constitutes an important and specialized profession that requires one to undergo a period of studying and training. Nonetheless, they failed to understand the specific roles and competencies of professionals in the field, or the scope of the profession. The field is also only deemed to be effective in a handful of sectors. It is perceived to have the greatest impact in areas traditionally associated with welfare such as family protection units, elderly care, and rehabilitation centers for people with disabilities. Nonetheless, its impact in institutions, schools, the healthcare sector, and the corrections system, remain unrecognized. The social and cultural perspectives on the profession also substantially limit the impact that it could have. Complex social and cultural attitudes shape the influence of social work limiting the full impact of the profession in Saudi society.

STUDY CONTRIBUTIONS

This study adds to the literature on the social work profession within the context of Saudi Arabia, and the Arab world to some extent. Social work remains a substantially understudied topic in these regions. The study also reveals specific areas where the profession is or is not deemed effective, findings that can be beneficial to policymakers and social work coordinators. These entities can utilize the findings of the current study to make decisions on resource allocation, and the improvement of institutional coordination to enable more impactful social work. Overall, the study contributes to understanding public perceptions on the influence of the profession, along with the societal barriers that limit the influence of the profession. The study provides a data-based picture of the current impact of social work while identifying some potential pathways to strengthen the acceptability of the profession to enable it sustain long term contributions to the Saudi society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Several initiatives could be undertaken to enhance the impact of social work on the Saudi society. Policymakers could strengthen institutional frameworks that target the integration of the profession into sectors that it has been identified to have minimal impact in, such as healthcare, education, and correctional services. Expanding social work into these sectors will contribute to the diversification of the impact of social work beyond the domains of welfare where its impact is noted to be visible. Policymakers, collaborating with social work practitioners could also undertake widespread public awareness campaigns on the role and impact of the discipline in the Saudi society to trigger a change in the cultural perceptions. Such

campaigns would address the social stigma associated with help seeking and the negative attitudes that have rendered social work incompatible with Islamic culture. They would subsequently contribute to breaking down key impediments to the impact of this profession.

LIMITATIONS

This study provides valuable insights on the impact of social work on Saudi society. Nonetheless, it harbors some limitations that may affect the reliability and validity of findings. The study used a convenience sample drawn from three cities, Riyadh, Medina, and Hail. And, while this sample size was sufficient for quantitative analysis, the findings it yielded may not be fully representative of the diversity of Saudi society across the kingdom. It is possible that less urbanized areas hold different views of the influence of the profession. The study is also limited by the exclusion of participants without university degrees. The exclusion hinders the generalizability of the findings, limiting their applicability to individuals who do not hold university degrees. The final limitation of the study is the use of only a quantitative approach, where a mixed methods approach incorporating qualitative analysis would offer richer insights on the effect of the discipline.

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